

Analytical Applications of 2-Propionyl-1-Naphthol Oxime: Part I. Reactions with Metal Ions and Gravimetric Determination of Copper

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[2-propionyl-1-naphthol oxime has been found to be a wide-spectrum precipitant for a number of metal ions. It also gives colour react ions with some ions. Cu^{2+} gives a buff coloured bis-chelate $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ precipitated at pH 1.5—2.5 insoluble in acetic and dil. mineral acids. From 10—40 mgms. of Cu^{2+} has been determined gravimetrically, the average error being less than 0.1 per cent. Determination of copper in the presence of moderate amounts of (10—20 mg.) of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} has been found to be satisfactory. The entrainment of Fe^{3+} by the Cu^{2+} chelate has been found to be eliminated using 1:1 ethanol: ether wash liquid].

The functioning of aromatic *o*-hydroximes as wide spectrum precipitants that are very pH dependant has been wellknown since the work of Ephraim¹ and later other workers²⁻⁷ on salicylaldoxime, one of the best known reagents of this class. A number of oximes of this class were soon examined by Ephraim⁸ who found them to be selective reagents for Cu^{2+} in weakly acid medium. Another prominent reagent of this class is resacetophenone oxime (Rapox) used by several workers.⁹⁻¹² It was found meanwhile that Schiff's bases formed by *o*-hydroxyaldehydes behave similarly as their oximes.¹³⁻¹⁴

The inference that the substitution of the benzene by the naphthalene ring in such reagents would lead to stronger π bonding of ligands with the metal ions due to increased conjugation followed from the relationship— $\log \beta_n = a p K_a + b$ proposed by Jones and Poole¹⁵ and its application to the Cu^{2+} chelates with substituted salicyldehydes by Clarke and co-workers¹⁶. Reagents in the naphthalene series should accordingly be more effective

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gravimetric and colorimetric reagents as compared with the corresponding members in the benzene series in virtue of the expected higher values of the overall stability constants (β_n) of the metal chelates formed by the naphthalene series members.

Merchant and Pishwika¹⁷ prepared 2-propionyl-1-naphthol oxime and from some preliminary work found it to be a promising reagent for Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} . Tambat¹⁸ carried

out a more complete study of the interactions of this reagent with metal ions and developed methods for gravimetric determination of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Co^{2+} and colorimetric determination of Fe^{3+} and Co^{2+} .

This paper incorporates the reactions of 2-propionyl-1-naphthol oxime with metal ions and its application for the gravimetric determination of copper and its separation from Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Fe^{3+} .

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade except α -naphthol and propionic acid. Stock solutions of metal ions, prepared by dissolving pure salts in double distilled water, were employed after standardisation by standard methods. 0.1M solutions of cations were employed in most cases, and pH was adjusted with acid or alkali depending upon the pH range.

Reagent: The ketone 2-propionyl-1-naphthol reported by various workers was prepared by condensing α -naphthol with propionic acid in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride by the method of Desai, Hamid and Shroff¹⁹ (m.p. 81°). The oxime as reported by Merchant and Pishwika (loc.cit.) was prepared in the usual manner and recrystallised from alcohol (m.p. 124°).

[Analysis found: C=72.2%, H=5.9%, N=6.5%; required: C=72.56%, H=6.05%, N=6.51%].

Reactions with metal ions: A one per cent ethanolic solution of reagent was employed for the tests. The initial pH of precipitation and the pH range of colour formation were noted and the results are summarised in table 1. The following metal ions were found to give no precipitate or colour formation— Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Ti^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , Th^{4+} , MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} .

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TABLE 1

Reactions of 2-propionyl-1-naphthol oxime with metal ions.

Ion tested	Interaction ppt. or colour	pH of incipient precipitation or pH range of colour formation
Pd ²⁺	Orange yellow ppt.	1
Cu ²⁺	buff precipitate	1.5
Fe ²⁺	dirty green precipitate	4
Fe ³⁺	green colour	2.2-4.5
	violet colour	4.5-5.8
Vo ₂ ¹⁺	brown colour	1
Au ³⁺	red colour	4
	green colour	7
Uo ₂ ²⁺	orange colour	4
Ni ²⁺	pale green precipitate	3
Co ²⁺	brown precipitate	5
Mn ²⁺	dark green precipitate	5.5
Cd ²⁺	pale yellow precipitate	6
Bj ³⁺	pale yellow precipitate	6
Pb ²⁺	pale yellow precipitate	5.5

Reactions with Ni²⁺, Pd²⁺, Co²⁺ and Fe³⁺ have been investigated in detail and analytical applications based on these will be published shortly.

Determination of Copper: The copper bis-chelate with the reagent, Cu(C₁₃H₁₂O₂N)₂ (Cu-12.93% (Calc), 12.87, found; N-5.63% (Calc), 5.64 found) precipitated at pH 2.0—2.5 (acetic acid + sodium acetate) is buff coloured and is insoluble in water, ethanol, ether, dil. acetic acid and sparingly soluble in dilute but fairly readily soluble in concentrated mineral acids on warming. It may be dried at 110—120°. Above 140° it decomposes.

Procedure for Determination of Copper: An aliquot of Cu²⁺ solution containing 10-40 mg. of copper is diluted to about 200 ml., pH adjusted to 2.5 with an acetate buffer and a calculated volume of one per cent ethanolic solution of reagent added with stirring followed by about ten per cent excess to ensure complete precipitation. The precipitate is digested at about 60°—70°, allowed to stand for about 20 minutes and then filtered through a sintered-bed (G₃ or G₄) crucible, washed with 50% ethanol, dried at 110-120° to a constant weight and weighed as Cu(C₁₃H₁₂O₂N)₂. Conversion factor for Cu²⁺—0.1293. Results (mean of analysis in duplicate) are given in table 2.

TABLE 2

Estimation of Copper

Cu ²⁺ taken mg.	Cu ²⁺ (found) mg.	% Error	Cu ²⁺ taken mg.	Cu ²⁺ (found) mg.	% Error
2.655	2.632	-0.87	23.90	23.92	+0.08
5.310	5.316	+0.48	26.55	26.57	+0.08
7.965	7.978	+0.16	29.21	29.22	+0.03
10.62	10.63	+0.09	31.82	31.83	+0.03
13.48	13.47	-0.07	34.52	34.52	0.00
15.93	15.92	-0.06	37.17	37.19	+0.05
18.59	18.60	+0.05	42.48	42.51	+0.07
21.24	21.24	0.00			

Table 1 indicates that the pH range in which the precipitation of Co^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Cd^{2+} begins is much above the pH of complete precipitation of Cu^{2+} whereas Zn^{2+} gives no precipitate. It should accordingly be possible to determine Cu^{2+} at pH 2.5 in the presence of these ions. Some preliminary experiments have confirmed this. Although the precipitation of Ni^{2+} starts at pH 3 its separation from Cu^{2+} at pH 2.5 is neat. Table 3 gives the results of determination of Cu^{2+} in the presence of moderate amounts of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} .

Fe^{3+} forms a green coloured soluble complex with the reagent in the pH range 2.2—4.0. Cu^{2+} if precipitated at pH 2.5 in the presence of Fe^{3+} entrains the latter slightly as indicated by the slightly higher weights of Cu^{2+} complex and by qualitative tests on its mineral acid solution. The entrainment can be reduced by using wash liquids like ethanol: water and almost removed with 1:1 ethanol: ether (diethyl) as shown in table 3.

TABLE 3

Estimation of Cu^{2+} in presence of other metals.

Metal ion	Amount of metal ion added (mg)	Cu^{2+} taken (mg)	Cu^{2+} found mg.	%Error
1 Zn^{2+}	10.0	10.62	10.63	+0.09
	20.0	10.62	10.61	-0.09
2 Cd^{2+}	10.0	10.62	10.64	+0.18
	20.0	10.62	10.63	-0.09
3 Co^{2+}	10.0	10.62	10.61	-0.09
	20.0	10.62	10.59	-0.20
4 Ni^{2+}	10.36	10.62	10.62	0.00
	20.72	10.62	10.61	-0.09
	10.36	21.24	21.23	-0.04
	20.72	21.24	21.26	+0.08
5 Fe^{3+}	1.0	5.015	5.043 ^a	+0.55
	2.0	5.015	5.047 ^a	+0.64
	4.0	5.015	5.065 ^a	+0.78
Fe^{3+}	5.0	20.06	20.17 ^b	+0.54
	6.0	20.06	20.13 ^b	+0.34
	8.0	20.06	20.09 ^c	+0.14
	7.0	10.30	10.29 ^c	-0.10
	7.0	10.30	10.31 ^c	+0.10

a — 50% ethanol used as wash liquid.

b — 75% ethanol used as wash liquid.

c — 1:1 ethanol: ether used as wash liquid.

DISCUSSION

The results given above show that 2-propionyl-1-naphthol oxime can be used for the gravimetric determination of from 10 to about 40 mg of Cu^{2+} at pH 2.5, the maximum

error being 0.1% (table 2). Also Cu^{2+} can be determined in presence of moderate amounts of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and small amounts of Fe^{3+} , if 1:1 ethanol: ether is used as wash liquid. Thus 2-propionyl-1-naphthol oxime affords a quick, simple and selective method for the determination of Cu^{2+} at pH 2.5 which compares well with existing gravimetric methods for Cu^{2+} ion.

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